

SINGLE VS DOUBLE DIGITAL BLOCK FOR FINGER LACERATION REPAIR, A COMPARATIVE STUDY

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Abstract

Background: Among hand injuries, most common are to the fingers. Local Anesthesia for laceration repair include Dorsal approach which involves infiltrating local anesthesia via two punctures whereas only a single prick is required in volar approach to anesthetize the finger for laceration repair.

Objective: To compare the outcomes of single-volar versus double-dorsal digital block in patients undergoing finger laceration repair.

Methods: In this randomized clinical trial, conducted from September 2022 to March 2023 at Department of Plastic Surgery, 80 patients were allocated to 2 Groups.

Group A (n=40) received double-dorsal subcutaneous injection into web space on each side of digit involved which blocked the proper digital and palmar digital nerves and Group B (n=40) were administered single volar subcutaneous injection at the base on volar aspect of the involved digit. Outcomes measured included anesthesia pain score (APS), suturing pain score (SPS), onset time of total anesthesia (OTTA), and rescue injection need (RIN). Data were analyzed using t-tests and chi-square/Fisher's exact tests; $p \leq 0.05$ was considered significant.

Results: Group B had significantly lower APS (4.87 ± 1.52 vs 7.42 ± 1.33 , $p < 0.001$) and SPS (1.70 ± 0.64 vs 4.10 ± 0.98 , $p < 0.001$) compared with Group A. OTTA was slightly longer in Group B (3.47 ± 0.59 vs 3.02 ± 0.80 min, $p = 0.006$). Rescue injections were required less frequently in Group B (7.5% vs 57.5%, $p < 0.001$).

Conclusion: Single-volar digital block provides effective anesthesia with less injection and suturing pain, fewer rescue injections, and is a suitable alternative to double- dorsal block for finger laceration repair.

INTRODUCTION

Hand injuries are a frequent reason for presentation to emergency departments, with reported incidences as high as 35% in some series [1]. These injuries are often occupational in origin and occur more

commonly in men [2,3]. The fingers and thumb represent the most commonly affected sites and account for a large share of emergency hand trauma [3]. Many digital lacerations can be managed safely in

the emergency setting under local/regional anesthesia, allowing the patient to remain awake (which facilitates communication) and often reducing hospital stay and resource use [4,5].

Adequate anesthesia for digital procedures may be achieved by simple local infiltration at the wound or by peripheral nerve blockade. Several digital block techniques are described in the literature, including the traditional double-dorsal (two-injection) block and single-injection approaches such as volar subcutaneous and transthecal blocks [6–10]. Comparative trials and reviews have addressed efficacy, patient comfort, onset time, and need for supplementary injections, but findings have been inconsistent across settings and populations [4,9,10]. The classical double-dorsal technique requires two punctures at the lateral bases of the digit to block the digital nerves; it is effective but often associated with greater injection discomfort and theoretical risk to the digital neurovascular bundle because of needle proximity to digital arteries [6,7]. To reduce these drawbacks, single-injection volar techniques were developed. Notably, the transthecal digital block – first reported by Chiu – involves injecting local anesthetic into the flexor tendon sheath at the volar crease so that the solution tracks along the sheath and anesthetizes the digital nerves circumferentially with a single puncture [11]. Modifications and clinical descriptions by Whetzel and others have refined the technique and suggested it offers comparable anesthesia with less injection pain and a lower risk of direct neurovascular trauma [12,13].

Clinical studies comparing single-injection transthecal/volar techniques with the traditional double-dorsal block have shown mixed results: some report lower injection pain and similar anesthesia success with single-injection methods, while others find no clear difference in efficacy or onset time [4,9,10]. Meta-analytic and randomized data therefore remain inconclusive for universal adoption, and concerns persist regarding occasional incomplete dorsal anesthesia (particularly over the thumb or proximal phalanx) after a single volar injection [4,10,14].

Given this background and the routine use of the double-dorsal block at our institution, we performed a randomized clinical trial comparing the single-

injection volar transthecal technique with the double-dorsal technique in patients undergoing finger laceration repair. Primary outcomes included anesthesia pain score at injection, suturing pain score, onset time of complete anesthesia, and the need for rescue injections. The study aims to clarify whether the transthecal approach provides equivalent anesthesia with improved patient comfort in our clinical setting.

Materials and Methods

This randomized clinical trial was conducted at the Department of Plastic Surgery, Karachi, over six months from 25th September 2022 to 24th March 2023. The study aimed to compare the outcomes of single versus double digital block in patients undergoing finger laceration repair. Informed consent was obtained from all participants.

The sample size was calculated using OpenEpi(<https://www.openepi.com/SampleSize/SSMean.htm>) based on reported mean onset times of anesthesia: 3.32 ± 0.42 minutes for single volar injection and 4.53 ± 0.57 minutes for double dorsal injection, with 80% power and 95% confidence level [9]. The calculated sample size was 6 patients; however, 80 patients (40 per group) were recruited to improve reliability. Non-probability consecutive sampling was used.

Patients were randomly assigned using a lottery method into two groups: Group A (Double-Dorsal Block): Two subcutaneous injections on either side of the finger, blocking proper digital and palmar digital nerves.

Group B (Single Volar Block): Single subcutaneous injection at the palmar base of the involved digit.

All injections used the same anesthetic type and dose and were administered by the same investigator. Primary outcomes included anesthesia pain score, suturing pain score, and time of onset of anesthesia, rescue injection needed and total duration of procedure.

Outcome Measures

The primary outcomes of this study included the anesthesia pain score (APS), suturing pain score (SPS), onset time of total anesthesia (OTTA), and the need for rescue injection (RIN). The APS reflected the pain perceived by the patient at the time of anesthetic injection, measured using the Visual

Analog Scale (VAS). The SPS represented the pain experienced during suturing after the administration of anesthesia, also assessed on the VAS. The OTTA was defined as the time interval from injection of local anesthetic to the complete loss of pinprick sensation in the digit. The RIN outcome measured the requirement for an additional dose of local anesthetic to continue suturing, which was

considered necessary if the VAS score exceeded 6. In such cases, pain was reassessed following administration of the rescue dose. The VAS, a validated tool for pain assessment, uses a 10-cm line anchored between “no pain” and “worst pain,” on which patients mark the intensity of pain they perceive.

Data Collection and Management

Patient demographics, injury characteristics, and outcome measures were recorded in a structured proforma. Confidentiality was maintained by storing data in a password-protected computer folder. Paper records were securely stored, accessible only to the principal investigator

Statistical Analysis

Continuous variables were expressed as mean \pm standard deviation or median (IQR) based on normality (Shapiro-Wilk test).

Categorical variables were presented as frequencies and percentages.

Comparisons: Independent t-test for normal continuous variables, Mann-Whitney U test for non-normal variables. Chi-square or Fisher's exact test for categorical variables.

Effect modifiers such as age, gender, injury site, laceration size, and procedure duration were controlled through stratification.

$p \leq 0.05$ was considered statistically significant.

Techniques

Two digital block techniques were employed in this study. Patients in Group A received the traditional double-dorsal digital block, which consisted of two subcutaneous injections of local anesthetic into the dorsal web spaces at the base of the affected digit

[Figure 1]. This approach targeted both the proper digital and palmar digital nerves bilaterally, providing circumferential anesthesia of the digit [6,9].

Patients in Group B received the single volar transthecal digital block, performed through a single injection into the flexor tendon sheath at the palmar aspect of the digit, just proximal to the A1 pulley [Figure 2]. First described by Chiu, the transthecal approach relies on diffusion of anesthetic solution along the tendon sheath to achieve blockade of all four digital nerves [15,16]. Cadaveric studies demonstrated that methylene blue injected into the tendon sheath diffused circumferentially to stain the epineurium of both volar and dorsal digital nerves [11,16,17]. Compared with dorsal injection, the transthecal technique reduces the number of punctures, may cause less injection pain, and minimizes the risk of neurovascular injury [6,14,18-20].

Figure 1: Double Dorsal Technique 1

Figure 2: Single Volar Technique 1

In both groups, the same type and dose of local anesthetic was administered by the principal investigator, and all procedures were performed under standard aseptic precautions

Results

A total of 80 patients were included, with 40 in each group. The mean age was comparable between groups (35.87 ± 13.33 years in Group A vs. 36.62 ± 13.12 years in Group B), with a male predominance in both (67.5% in Group A vs. 57.5% in Group B). Right-sided lacerations were slightly more frequent

(52.5% in Group A vs. 60% in Group B). The middle finger was the most commonly injured site, accounting for 25% of cases in Group A and 37.5% in Group B. Mean laceration length was 2.27 cm in both groups, while mean procedure duration was slightly shorter in Group B (32.85 ± 8.30 minutes) compared to Group A (34.95 ± 7.62 minutes). (Table 1) Pain and anesthesia outcomes showed significant differences. Group A (double-dorsal block) reported higher mean anesthesia pain scores (7.42 ± 1.33 vs. 4.87 ± 1.52, $p < 0.001$) and

suturing pain scores (4.10 ± 0.98 vs. 1.70 ± 0.64 , $p < 0.001$) compared with Group B (single-volar block). The onset of total anesthesia was slightly faster in Group A (3.02 ± 0.80 minutes vs. 3.47 ± 0.59 minutes, $p = 0.008$).

Rescue injection was required more frequently in Group A (57.5%) than Group B (7.5%) ($p < 0.001$). (Table 2)

Discussion

Each digit receives sensory innervation from four digital nerves—two volar and two dorsal—that must be effectively targeted for adequate anesthesia. The traditional two-injection dorsal block has been widely used but is associated with greater pain during administration and a higher risk of neurovascular injury. More recently, single volar subcutaneous injection techniques have been developed to reduce injection pain while maintaining anesthetic efficacy.

In our study, we compared the single-injection volar technique with the two-injection dorsal technique in patients undergoing finger laceration repair. The single volar injection group demonstrated significantly lower anesthesia pain scores, suturing pain scores, and a reduced need for rescue injections,

with comparable onset time of anesthesia. These findings are consistent with prior work by Low et al. and Chiu, who described volar and transthecal techniques designed to minimize discomfort and avoid neurovascular injury [11,14-17].

Several studies have reported that single-injection techniques achieve similar anesthesia success as dorsal blocks while improving patient comfort [14,21,22].

Meta-analyses have also suggested that volar approaches may occasionally provide incomplete anesthesia to the dorsal aspect of the thumb or proximal phalanx, but overall results show lower pain scores and higher patient and physician satisfaction with volar techniques [14,20,21,23-25]. Our findings reinforce this trend, supporting the use of single-injection volar blocks as a safe and effective alternative to the traditional approach.

Despite this, variations in study design, sample size, and pain scoring methods across the literature introduce some heterogeneity in reported outcomes. Nevertheless, the consistent observation of lower injection pain with volar techniques highlights their clinical advantage, particularly in emergency settings where patient comfort and procedural efficiency are critical.

Table 1. Baseline characteristics of study participants (n=80)

Variable	Group A (Double dorsal)	Group B (Single Volar)	Total	P-Value
Age (Years, Mean +/- SD)	35.9 ± 13.3	36.6 ± 13.1	36.2 ± 13.2	0.78
Gender (Male/Female)	27 (67.5%) / 13 (32.5%)	23 (57.5%) / 17 (42.5%)	50/30	0.34
Hand Side (Right/Left)	21 (52.5%) / 19 (47.5%)	24 (60%) / 16 (40%)	45 / 35	0.48
Most Common Finger	Middle finger (25%) & Ring finger (25%)	Middle finger (37.5%)	-	-
Mean Laceration Length (cm)	2.27 ± 0.93	2.27 ± 1.06	-	-

Mean Procedure Duration (min)	34.95 ± 7.62	32.85 ± 8.3	-	-
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Table 2. Comparison of key outcomes between gro(n=80)

Outcome	Group A (Double Dorsal)	Group B (Single Volar)	P-Value
Anesthesia Pain Score (mean ± SD)	7.4 ± 1.3	4.9 ± 1.5	<0.001
Suturing Pain Score (mean ± SD)	4.1 ± 1.0	1.7 ± 0.6	<0.001
Onset Time (min, mean ± SD)	3.0 ± 0.8	3.5 ± 0.6	0.006
Rescue Injection Required	23 (57.5%)	3 (7.5%)	<0.001

Conclusion

The findings of this study indicate that the single-injection volar subcutaneous digital block is as effective and safe as the traditional double-dorsal injection technique for finger laceration repair. It provides comparable anesthesia and suturing pain scores, similar onset of anesthesia, and a reduced need for multiple injections. Therefore, the single-volar injection can be considered a reliable and convenient alternative for digital anesthesia in clinical practice.

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